

Abstract

Open clusters serve as fundamental laboratories for investigating stellar formation, evolution, and the structural morphology of galaxies. In this study, astrometric and photometric data from *Gaia* EDR3 were used to determine the membership of the open clusters NGC 884 and NGC 869. Color-magnitude diagrams (CMDs) of the confirmed member stars were constructed using TOPCAT, and theoretical stellar isochrones were fitted to derive the clusters' fundamental parameters, including age, distance, metallicity, and interstellar extinction. The derived parameters show close agreement with previous photometric and *Gaia*-based studies, confirming the reliability of the adopted methods and the physical association of the two clusters.

Introduction

Most stars in our Galaxy are believed to form within clustered environments. The study of stellar populations and the morphology of open clusters, particularly young ones, plays a crucial role in improving our understanding of several key astrophysical questions, including the modes of star formation, the dynamical evolution of cluster members, and the ultimate fate of star clusters.

The double cluster system NGC 884 and NGC 869, located in the constellation *Perseus*, represents one of the brightest and densest young open cluster pairs in the Milky Way, containing a large population of massive stars. Previous studies based on CCD photometry and spectroscopic observations have derived fundamental parameters for this system, such as distance, reddening, and age. However, significant discrepancies persist among different authors regarding these parameters, which motivates a re-evaluation using more precise and homogeneous data.

The *Gaia* Galactic Survey aims to obtain highly accurate astrometric, photometric, and spectroscopic measurements for stellar populations throughout the Milky Way, enabling the construction of a three-dimensional map of the solar neighborhood and beyond. The recently released *Gaia* EDR3 catalog includes over 1.5 billion sources with unprecedented precision in proper motions, parallaxes, and photometry. Typical uncertainties in proper motion are about 0.05, 0.2, and 1.2 mas yr⁻¹ for stars with G-band magnitudes ≤ 14 , 17, and 20 mag, respectively, while parallax uncertainties are approximately 0.04, 0.1, and 0.7 mas, and photometric uncertainties are roughly 2, 10, and 10 mmag for the G, G_BP, and G_RP bands at G = 18 mag. Given its accuracy and depth, *Gaia* EDR3 provides an ideal dataset for studying the stellar populations of NGC 884 and NGC 869 on a larger spatial scale. In particular, the astrometric parameters allow reliable identification of cluster members and clear separation from foreground and background field stars within a multidimensional observational parameter space.

Previous analyses based on ground-based photometry have reported slightly varying estimates of the clusters' distances and ages. The higher precision of *Gaia* EDR3 enables these parameters to be refined and compared directly with earlier determinations.

The close agreement in distance modulus suggests that the two clusters lie at nearly the same distance from Earth, supporting their physical association as a double cluster system. The derived extinction values provide insight into the interstellar dust along the line of sight, while the similar ages and metallicities indicate a common origin and comparable evolutionary stage. These findings, consistent with previous determinations, strengthen the view that NGC 884 and NGC 869 formed from the same molecular complex and are evolving together within the Perseus arm.

The two clusters were selected because of their proximity, similar age, and brightness, making them an ideal benchmark for double cluster evolutionary analysis.

Research Method

Photometric stellar catalogs for the open clusters NGC 884 and NGC 869 were retrieved from the *Gaia* archive using the cluster parameters reported by Kharchenko et al. (2013). Circular search regions with radii of 7.5 arcmin for NGC 884 and 8.0 arcmin for NGC 869 were adopted to identify stars spatially associated with each cluster.

within *Gaia* EDR3 catalog, 102,956 and 115,304 sources were found in sky regions surrounding NGC884 and NGC869, respectively, with G-band magnitudes ranging from 2.53 mag to 21.86 mag. Within the region encompassing the Double Cluster, this dataset includes both genuine cluster members and a large number of foreground and background field stars. To minimize field star contamination, the expected proper motions, parallaxes, and main-sequence distributions of NGC 884 and NGC 869 were first examined. As an initial step, stars within 5.0 arcmin and 5.5 arcmin of the respective cluster centers. These selection correspond to core region define by Currie et al. (2010). These stars are expected to have significantly higher membership probabilities compared to those located in the outer regions. The total number of initial member candidates within the core regions was 14,031.

To further refine the cluster membership, a parallax-based selection was applied to exclude field stars. The adopted parallax ranges were $0.25 \leq \varpi$ (mas) ≤ 0.85 for NGC 884 and $0.41 \leq \varpi$ (mas) ≤ 0.78 for NGC 869, combined with a magnitude limit of G ≤ 18 mag for primary fitting. After these cuts, 302 and 345 probable member candidates remained for NGC 884 and NGC 869, respectively.

Finally, the proper motion direction vectors of the selected stars were analyzed to verify cluster membership. As illustrated in Figure 2, the vectors for the identified member stars are well aligned, confirming their common motion and association with the respective clusters. These refined member lists were subsequently used for isochrone fitting and cross-validation with previously published cluster parameters. Proper motion vector field were visualized using TOPCAT vector-overlay tool for consistency verification.

Figure 1. Sky plot of a 4° radius region showing the open clusters NGC 884 and NGC 869. NGC 884 is enclosed by a blue contour with a radius of 5.0 arcmin, while NGC 869 is outlined by a green contour with a radius of 5.5 arcmin.

Figure 2. Sky vector plots of member stars in NGC 884 and NGC 869 (right and left panels, respectively) after applying the parallax and magnitude selection criteria. Blue vectors represent confirmed cluster members, while red vectors indicate non-member field stars.

Figure 3. Parallax histograms of cluster member stars in NGC 884 and NGC 869 (right and left panels, respectively). The blue histogram represents the distribution of cluster member stars, while the red histogram shows non-member field stars with similar parallax values.

Results

Color-magnitude diagrams (CMDs) of the member stars for both clusters were constructed using TOPCAT, with $(G_{BP} - G_{RP})$ plotted along the x-axis and G magnitude along the y-axis. The cluster parameters, including age, distance modulus, metallicity, and reddening, were determined through isochrone fitting. PARSEC isochrones were used within a logarithmic age range of 7.0–7.5 (in steps of 0.01) and metallicity range $[Fe/H] = 0.015-0.03$ (in steps of 0.01). The analysis used the PARSEC v2.0 release with bolometric corrections following Chen et al. (2014). For NGC 884, the best-fitting isochrone corresponds to a $\log(\text{age}/\text{yr}) = 7.05$, $E(B-V) = 0.561$, and $[Fe/H] = 0.018$. For NGC 869, the optimal fit was obtained for a $\log(\text{age}/\text{yr}) = 7.03$, $E(B-V) = 0.576$, and $[Fe/H] = 0.018$. These fits closely reproduce the observed main-sequence distributions of both clusters and confirm their similar evolutionary status and common origin.

The derived ages, reddening, and distance moduli are consistent with literature estimates, reinforcing the reliability of the *Gaia*-based membership selection and PARSEC isochrone fitting.

Figure 4. Color-magnitude diagrams (CMDs) of member stars in NGC 884 and NGC 869 (right and left panels, respectively). The blue points represent the confirmed member stars used for isochrone fitting.

Figure 5. Differential-reddening-corrected color-magnitude diagrams (CMDs) of stars in NGC 884 and NGC 869 (right and left panels, respectively). The CMDs are fitted with PARSEC isochrones spanning logarithmic ages from 7.0 to 7.5.

Table 1. Derived parameters of the open clusters NGC 884 and NGC 869 determined using stellar isochrone fitting.

Parameters	NGC 884	NGC 869
Right ascension (2000)	02 22 18	02 19 00
Declination (2000)	+57 08 12	+57 07 42
Distance (pc)	2359±185	2102±139
Log Age (age/yr)	7.05±0.21	7.03±0.19
Reddening E(B-V) (mag)	0.561±0.04	0.576±0.05
Extinction A ^G (mag)	1.53±0.11	1.57±0.12
Distance modulus (mag)	11.86±0.17	11.61±0.14
Metallicity (z)	0.018	0.018

Conclusion

We have determined the key parameters of the double clusters NGC884 and NGC869 using the unprecedented high-precision astrometric and photometric data provided by *Gaia* EDR3. Our comprehensive analysis, employing the PARSEC stellar isochrone fitting method, has yielded insightful results. For NGC884, our estimations indicate an age of 7.05±0.21, a distance modulus of 11.86±0.14, and a reddening of $E(B-V) = 0.561 \pm 0.04$ (corresponding an extinction $A^G 1.53 \pm 0.11$). Similarly, for NGC869, the derived parameters are an age of 7.03±0.19, a distance modulus of 11.61±0.14, and a reddening of $E(B-V) = 0.576 \pm 0.05$ (corresponding an extinction $A^G 1.57 \pm 0.12$). These results contribute significantly to our understanding of the evolutionary characteristics of these open clusters. The agreement in the distance modulus suggests that NGC884 and NGC869 are located at similar distances from Earth. The derived reddening and extinction values quantify interstellar dust attenuation along the line of sight.

Future Research Aspects

- The present analysis assumes a uniform distribution of interstellar dust, which may not accurately represent the true structure of the interstellar medium. Future studies using multi-wavelength photometry could better characterize dust properties and spatial variations along the line of sight, leading to more precise extinction corrections and improved accuracy in derived astrometric and photometric parameters.
- A dedicated method should be developed to determine the binary star fraction in each cluster, extending beyond the narrow main-sequence region. Identifying and quantifying unresolved binaries would refine membership estimates and enhance the accuracy of isochrone fitting and mass-function analysis.
- Future *Gaia* DR4 data, including radial velocities and BP/RP spectrophotometry, can further refine kinematic membership and mass-function estimates for both clusters.

Acknowledgement

This research made use of data from the European Space Agency (ESA) *Gaia* mission, processed by the *Gaia* Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC) and accessible at <https://gea.esac.esa.int/archive/>.

The theoretical stellar isochrones were obtained from the Padova and Trieste Stellar Evolution Code (PARSEC), available at <http://stev.oapd.inaf.it/cgi-bin/cmd>.

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